

Basilica of San Vitale

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The Church of San Vitale, located in northwestern Ravenna, is the nearest known relative of the church of Saints Sergius and Bacchus built by Justinian in Constantinople around the same time, although the latter had not served as a direct model. The basilica was initially the martyrium of Saint Vitalis, the patron of Ravenna. Before the mid-tenth century, but unknown exactly when, the church was acquired by a Benedictine monastery, to which it belonged until 1860, when it was dissolved. The basilica of San Vitale was erected during the reign of Justinian (527-565). Julianus Argentarius, a Greek-speaking local banker and architect, sponsored the construction commanded by bishop Ecclesius (521-532). The church was consecrated by bishop Maximian in 547. However, bishop Victor (538-545) was most probably the person who has played a substantial role in the construction of the basilica, as his monogram appear in many places. The architectural design but also the decoration of San Vitale were influenced by the latest trends in Constantinople. Even though Ravenna was at the time the capital of the Ostrogoth kingdom, it was heavily influenced by Byzantium. The basilica is octagonal. It has a diameter of c. 40 m., while its octagonal naos has eight inner piers joined by arches that support the dome. The central section is surrounded by two superposed ambulatories. One of the arches leads to the presbytery and the apse. It has also two rooms with apse and domed chapels. The south one has sheltered the tombs of bishops Ecclesius, Ursicinus, and Victor. Although most parts of the original building have survived, the vaults replaced the wooden ceilings of the ambulatory and the gallery. The exterior buttresses were added perhaps in the late 12th century. The southern stair tower was transformed into a bell tower, which collapsed in 1688. The basilica was restored in the 16th century and chapels were created in the 18th century. In the early 20th century the basilica was excavated and reconstructed in its presumed original form. A small rectangular chapel was discovered under the original floor, presumably the 5th-century martyrium of St. Vitalis. San Vitale was decorated with marble wall revetment, mosaics and marble pavements, columns and capitals, stucco decoration, painted glass windows, and figural mosaics. It also had marble liturgical furnishings, including an altar, ciborium, and transennae, currently exhibited at the Museo Nazionale. The original columns, capitals, and impost blocks are still in place, but most of the wall revetments and pavements are modern reconstructions. Part of the floor decoration was remade in the 1540s, while the other two were repaired in the early 18th century. In 1931, excavation revealed two segments of the original floor, after which the entire level was lowered to the original level. The apse and presbytery floor were created between the 1910s-1930s. The apse, the walls of the presbytery and the triumphal arch are covered with mosaics. They presumably predate by a couple of years the consecration of the basilica in 547, though the panel with Justinian and bishop Maximian was perhaps made around the time of the consecration. It is possible that the dome was originally decorated with mosaics, although there are no traces left. A series of mosaics in the lunettes above the triforia depict scenes of sacrifices from the Old Testament. Each lunette is decorated by a pair of angels holding a medallion with a cross. On the walls, next to the windows are depicted the four Evangelists below their symbols. The vault of the presbytery is decorated with leaves, fruits and flowers, forming a crown around the Lamb of God. The crown is supported by four angels. Above the arches, two angels hold a disc and beside them are represented the cities of Jerusalem and Bethlehem. The intrados of the great triumphal arch is decorated with fifteen medallions (Jesus Christ, twelve Apostles, the sons of Saint Vitale: Saint Gervasius and Saint Protasius). The Theophany which has begun in 525 under bishop Ecclesius has a great gold fascia with twining flowers, birds, and cornucopia. In the apse, Christ is depicted seated, flanked by angels, offering the martyr's crown to Saint Vitale, while on his left, bishop Ecclesius offers a model of the

church. Lower is depicted the Emperor Justinian I with generals Belisarius and Narses, bishop Maximian, guards and deacons. The name of bishop Maximian was added later, suggesting that the composition may have been modified ca. 547. On the opposite wall is depicted Empress Theodora with court women and eunuchs. The basilica is one of the eight Early Christian monuments of Ravenna that were inscribed in 1996 in the UNESCO List of World Heritage Sites.

Date Range: 527 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Basilica of San Vitale, Ravenna

Region tags: Italy, Ravenna

Basilica of San Vitale, Ravenna

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Von Simson, O. Sacred Fortress: Byzantine Art and Statecraft in Ravenna. New Jersey, 1987.
- Source 2: Johnson, M. J. San Vitale in Ravenna and Octagonal Churches in Late Antiquity. Wiesbaden, 2018.
- Source 3: Andreescu-Treadgold, I., and W. Treadgold. "Procopius and the Imperial Panels of S. Vitale." The Art Bulletin 79, no. 4 (1997).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.ravennamosaici.it/basilica-di-san-vitale/>
- Source 1 Description: Official website
- Source 2 URL: <https://youtu.be/pytUlajVxGk>
- Source 2 Description: Interior of the basilica (video)
- Source 3 URL: <https://youtu.be/KTJiljqimCw>
- Source 3 Description: Ravenna basilica (exterior and interior simply presented)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1900-1940

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: N/A

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The city of Ravenna is located 10 km from the coast (Adriatic sea).

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Hexagon

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The basilica was not reconstructed. However, it was built over the 5th-century Martirium of Saint Vitalis.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Private individual

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Priests

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: Place of martyrdom of Saint Vitale

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– I don't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Glass tesserae for the mosaics

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

Notes: Jesus Christ is also depicted though.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Angels.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The non-figural decoration includes floral motifs, geometric motifs, animals, birds, fruits e.a.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The reliefs are purely decorative.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: A series of mosaics in the lunettes above the triforia depict scenes of sacrifices from the Old Testament.

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The decoration is rich including plants, flowers, fruits, birds, cornucopia.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The inscriptions always designate the persons depicted or describe the narrative scene.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Angels

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Cross, Theophany, Lamb of God.

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: In the lunettes above the triforia are depicted scenes of sacrifices from the Old Testament.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Emperor Justinian I is depicted with generals Belisarius and Narses, bishop Maximian, guards and deacons. On the opposite wall is depicted Empress Theodora with court women and eunuchs.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: This is not a burial. It was though built to honour Saint Vitalis, martyred at this same place.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The south chapel has sheltered the tombs of bishops Ecclesius, Ursicinus, and Victor.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: It is required for preserving the monument.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: For the preservation of the basilica repairs are taking indeed place periodically.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– I don't know

Notes: The maintenance is performed by experts from different disciplines, which is possibly permanent staff.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The basilica is also digitised and monitored with the aid of new technological tools.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: The basilica although in the past was a pilgrimage place, it is currently mostly visited by tourists.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: The monument belongs to the Diocese of Ravenna.

↳ Present part time

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Most probably male.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Notes: However, since the monument belongs to the Diocese of Ravenna, there is an hierarchy indeed.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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